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Objective: *To provide hierarchy of sources of law in your country and describe the role of the Constitution in this system*

Problem discussion : *Hierarchy of sources of law on the example of various legal orders*

«Hierarchy of sources of law and role of the Constitution in Ukrainian legal system»

As we have found out in the previous lectures and essays, law plays one of the most important roles in the life of society. Regardless of culture, religion and customs, positive law is the main formal legal source of regulation in the vast majority of countries in the world. But besides the letter of the law, there are many other informal factors, such as custom law, which regulate the norms of behavior and the concept of moral and ethical standards. However, above all of the above concepts is a document that is the most important for each state - the Constitution. Understanding and knowledge of the hierarchy of sources of law is necessary for the formation of a clear idea of jurisprudence and its further study, since knowledge of the structure of sources of law is the basis for all legal research.

The primary source of law in Ukraine is the Constitution. Constitution is the basis law with special content and structure that had the highest legal force in the country. The norms of the constitution have priority over the norms of laws and other regulatory legal acts. Constitution is not only the highest legal source, but also a main source of constitutional law - a fundamental branch of national law, is a set of legal norms that establish the foundations of the political and economic organization of society, the form of the state, the order and principles of the formation and competence of state authorities, the foundations of the legal status of a person and a citizen.

Second most important aspect and source of law in Ukraine is legal act - official written document adopted by an authorized body of the state or by other structures under its authority, which establishes, changes or cancels legal norms, or implements or interprets them. Legal act should always be documented and accepted by a clearly defined subject within the limits of his authority or by special permission. It establishes, changes or specifies legal prescriptions with the goal to regulate social relations by establishing subjective rights, legal obligations and prohibitions. Legal acts are divided into individual acts and normative legal acts. In the legal system of Ukraine, the normative legal act is one of the main sources of law.

The Ukrainian legal system belongs to the Romano-Germanic legal family, therefore, unlike countries with the Anglo-Saxon system, legal precedent does not play such an important role

in Ukraine. However, individual decisions of the Constitutional Court and the Supreme Court of Ukraine can be used to specify laws and close gaps in them, and therefore it would be logical to mark them as "quasi-precedents of interpretation", since judicial practice can also be considered one of the sources of law.

The last, but not the least aspect that need to be mentioned - the custom law. In Ukraine custom law has a rich history beginning from the Rus' Law in the mediaval times, but when the Soviet regime came to Ukraine legal doctrine changed and custom law was denied to be a source of legal regulation of social relations, allowing its use only in international law. However, after Ukraine gained independence, in the process of in-depth reformation of all branches of law, customary law is gaining more and more importance in the national legal system. Nowadays custom law is considered as a source of civil law in Ukraine as an accepted norms of behavior and civil-legal relationships.

In conclusion, the sources of law have a clear and distinct hierarchy and structure that allows the legal system to function properly. As in the case with a legislative process , there is a certain sequence of legal sources, each of which is applied in certain areas and situations. Understanding this hierarchy allows a more comprehensive understanding of legal processes and makes it possible to study them deeper based on knowledge of their origins. Also, the above knowledge makes it possible to reason about the judicial, constitutional and legislative systems at a more fundamental level.

Sources :

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